

PROMOTION OF PREVENTION OF OBESITY AMONG SCHOOL CHILDREN IN
THE PRIMARY HEALTH CARE SYSTEM.

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Abstract: Obesity is excessive accumulation of fats in the body. This pathology appears when the body weight increases by 20% or more. In this case, the patient suffers not only psychologically, but also from pathologies of internal organs. Today, obesity is a global epidemic, as people at any age are faced with obesity. Treatment of this disease includes physical activity, adherence to diet, medication and correction of psychoemotional conditions.

Key words: etiopathogenesis, metabolism, body mass index, diet, bariatrics

Obesity is subcutaneous fat as a result of metabolic disorders in the body accumulation of fats in the layer and tissues. Obesity is a common disease 50% in women, 30% in men, and 10% in children. 70 the average weight decreases with age. It causes obesity factors: excessive food consumption, especially rich in carbohydrates and fats excessive consumption of products, addiction to alcoholic beverages, physical inactivity; 40 includes older age, genetic predisposition. The autonomic nervous system in the development of obesity metabolism due to increased tone of the parasympathetic (department) of the system reduction is significant. This condition produces insulin from the pancreas increases excretion and causes obesity. The main cause of obesity pathogenetic mechanism is the energy entering and expending in the organism imbalance. This condition is more likely to be due to poor nutrition: fat in food and excess of carbohydrates, violation of the diet - daily calories the main part is related to its reception in the evening. Adipose tissue is the main storehouse of energy. Excess energy as triglycerides accumulates in adipocytes. Energy expenditure in the origin of obesity disorder is also very important, this condition is caused by various enzymatic and metabolic defects, violation of oxidation processes is related to the state of sympathetic innervation. In healthy, normal-weight people, overeating is the key to metabolism leads to an adaptive acceleration of exchange, that is, the main exchange is energy is a kind of buffer that keeps the balance, the amount of food taken maintains stability of body weight when it changes.

Many people do not know that there are two types of adipose tissue in the human body: gray and white adipose tissue. Gray adipose tissue is produced by mitochondria in cells. It is gray tissue that provides warmth to a person when he is not moving. These tissues accumulate around the thyroid gland and around the kidneys. It accumulates in a mixed manner in the chest area and in the shoulder area, between the shoulder blades. A significant accumulation of fat is explained by the increase in white adipose tissue. These tissues are made up of fat cells (adipocytes) and have the appearance of a large bubble, the nucleus of which is located in the periphery, not in the center. Such fat cells accumulate a lot under the skin, especially in the abdomen. The fat layer in the abdominal area can be 20 cm or more thick in some cases. In addition, there is an organ that accumulates fat in the abdominal cavity - charvi. Fat cells are also located in the area behind the abdomen, around the pancreas, aorta, and kidneys.

To ensure energy balance, the demand for energy is equal to its consumption should be done. Individual energy consumption in a person depends on three factors:

1) basic metabolism, proportionality of body weight and surface area, keeping the main physiological function

appropriateness of energy expenditure while standing;

2) thermogenic effect (special dynamic effect of food), approx

It is 5-10% and additional energy consumption during digestion and production of new substrate

It is related to the stimulation of metabolism.

3) physical activity causes a significant change in energy expenditure. High calorie. Eating food is one of the obvious causes of obesity. The second is without problems one of the reasons is a decrease in energy consumption, insufficient physical activity. Simple it is known from mathematical calculations that one excessive intake of food, for example, a sandwich with cheese in one day, a glass of milk in 10 years will lead to 10 kg of weight gain will come. Obesity and related complications in the development of adipose tissue in recent years its development is becoming more important.

Even the coronavirus infection that has spread all over the world today especially in overweight people it becomes difficult and in many cases with death is being completed. Don't worry, there are ways to prevent this disease: Eat healthy, doing physical education, giving up tobacco and alcohol products is enough. Cardiovascular diseases, strokes, malignant tumors, breathing through walking non-infectious diseases such as chronic diseases of organs and diabetes diseases are prevented. It is clear that human health depends on body weight in every way. Efforts have been made to switch to a healthy lifestyle in Uzbekistan. "Healthy lifestyle" adopted by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev measures for wide implementation and further development of public sports on" is also dedicated to the same issue. Especially the officials in this regard should be an example to the people. Money for citizens who walk the most every month award will be given. So, run in the morning, eat right.

Summary. Today, it is difficult to treat obesity and its effectiveness is quite low remains. It is a multifactorial disease. Obesity has been medical for many years not being considered a problem, but rather with the fact that the appearance of the disorder is in the first place is important. During the treatment, the goal is to return to the original weight. But this requires more difficult treatment measures. Treatment plan divided into parts and will be long-term. It should be taken into account that long-term treatment and planned treatment perfect types of measures do not yet exist. Obesity is fast, requiring constant monitoring and long-term treatment relapsing chronic disease. Short-term therapy is less effective and is discontinued then the disease recurs. It's not just the body in treating obesity and high body weight reduction, but also complete control of metabolic stress, serious diseases prevention of development, prevention of recurrence of obesity and long-lasting results saving time is the main strategic goal.

References:

1. Dedov.I.I., Melnichenko.G.A, Fadeyev.V.V. Endocrinology. 2000g
2. Dedov.I.I., Fadeyev.V.V. "Vvedeniye Endocrinology" (Rukovodstvo dlya vrachey). M.: "Bereg", 1998.
3. Harrison.T.R. Classical modern medicine. Internal diseases. Kniga shestaya. Moscow.: "Praktika". 2005g.
4. Chazov.Ye.I., Dedov I.I. Rukovodstvo po vnutrennim boleznyam. Moscow. "Medicine" 2000g.